

Participation of families in Inclusive Education in the first cycle of Basic Education: A Systematic Review

Title	Authors, year and country	Sample	Keywords	Purpose or issues.	Instrument and methodology	Main results	Bibliography
The participation of the families of students with disabilities in the university	Condoya, Navaza, & Duchia, Quito. (2020)	1120 students and families	Inclusion, family, university, humanity, autonomy, independence	The objective of this research is to show how the family of students with disabilities participates in the university educational process and how the participation of the family contributes to the achievement of the achievements of the student with some type of disability.	Qualitative methodology. Instrument: Interview and semi-structured conversations.	Concludes that the existence is important of a program for the inclusion of this group of students in the university and that its influence is positive, since it gives them backing and support in academic terms and social. Families point out that it provides them with a space in which they feel welcome, understood and considered, in which, in addition, they know and interact with other families who also have someone with a disability, so they don't feel alone.	Condoya, M.G., Navasa, M.G., Duchia, A. (2020). The participation of the families of students with disabilities in the university <i>Estudios Pedagógicos</i> XLVI, N° 3: 141-149, 2020 DOI:10.4067/S071807052020000300141 http://revistas.uach.cl/index.php/esped/article/view/6524/7632
Participation of families, tutorial action and guidance from a social justice approach	Bellido-Cala, Espanha (2021)	32 teachers	Guidance, participation, tutorial action, social justice, Grounded Theory	Identify whether social justice, from the participatory dimension, is present in the educational practice and discourse of professionals.	Qualitative methodology Instrument: Semi-structured interview.	-The participation of families does not occur significantly. - Families' routine is one of the reasons that keep them from participating in school.	Bellido-Cala, J.A. (2021). Participación de las familias, acción tutorial y orientación desde la justicia social. <i>Revista Española de Orientación y Psicopedagogía</i> , 32(1), 76-91. https://doi.org/10.5944/reop.vol.32.num.1.2021.30741

<p>The Relationship between Distributed Leadership and Family Involvement from Parents' Perspective*</p>	<p>Erol & Turhan, Turquia (2018)</p>	<p>1488 parents</p>	<p>Distributed leadership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Family involvement Secondary schools School-family partnership Parents' perspective </p>	<p>Identify the relationship between the perception of distributed parental leadership and family involvement. 1-To what level is distributed leadership applied in secondary schools according to parental views? 2-What is the level of parental involvement in schools? 3-There is a significant relationship between parents' distributed leadership perceptions and the level of understanding?</p>	<p>Correlational study. The Distributed Leadership Perception Scale for Parents (DLPSP) and the Parent Family Involvement Questionnaire were used as data collection tools in the research</p>	<p>With respect to family involvement, it was discovered that home-based involvement of the parents was high, school-family cooperation-based involvement was moderate, and school-based involvement was low. The involvement of parents in the school are strengthened by the implementation of the understanding of distributed leadership in schools</p>	<p>Erol, Y. C., & Turhan, M. (2018). The relationship between distributed leadership and family involvement from parents' perspective. <i>Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice</i>, 18, 525–540. DOI10.12738/estp.2018.3.0088 https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1202206</p>
<p>The Views and Attitudes of the Teacher Candidates</p>	<p>Kahraman, Turquia (2018)</p>	<p>1200 teachers</p>	<p>Family participation, preschool, elementary school teaching,</p>	<p>The investigate the views and the attitudes of the elementary education teacher candidates towards family</p>	<p>This research was carried out with descriptive information. Questionnaire and Scale of</p>	<p>The participation of families is not adequately included. - Families claim that communications were more in school meetings.</p>	<p>Kahraman, P. B. (2018). The Views and Attitudes of the Teacher Candidates from Preschool and Elementary School Teaching Departments toward Family Participation. <i>International</i></p>

es from Preschool and Elementary School Teaching Departments toward Family Participation			teacher candidates	participation. In addition, with this research it was attempted to determine whether the grades of the teacher candidates cause a common effect on their attitudes towards family participation according to their department.	Family Participation for Teacher Candidates, developed by Yavuz Güler (2014).	- Teachers claim that the participation of families contributes to the child's school development.	<i>Journal of Progressive Education</i> , v14, n3, DOI:10.29329/ijpe.2018.146.4 https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1186530.pdf
Families at the heart of inclusive education	Rueda & Fernández (2019)	Does not describe	Inclusive education, rights, participation, family voices.	Analyzes the role that families must play in transforming educational systems and contexts to be more inclusive.	Document analysis.	-The participation of the family to be supportive is to build a collaborative relationship where the agents exchange information and share knowledge to work together to achieve a common goal.	Rueda, C. S., & Fernández, A.B. (2019). Families at the heart of inclusive education. <i>Open Classroom</i> , 48 (1), 51–58. https://doi.org/10.17811/rife.48.1.2019.51-58
Barriers to Parental/Family Participation in the Education of a Child with Disabilities in Kenya	Odongo, Quênia (2018)	Documents, research reactors and observations	Special Needs Education, Disabilities, Inclusive Education, Community Based Programs, Special Schools & Integrated Units.	Identify barriers to parental/family involvement in children's education a child with a disability and will suggest possible steps to empower families of children with disability to take active roles in their education	Observations, reports and research	-Some parents are misinformed about who can help their child with a disability. -Lack of adequate policy and funding, combined with cultural attitudes towards individuals with disabilities, continued to hamper efforts to implement inclusion.	Odongo, G. (2018). Barriers to Parental/Family Participation in the Education of a Child with Disabilities in Kenya. <i>International Journal Of Special Education</i> , 33 (1). https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1184076.pdf

<p>A Study on the Effects to Students' STEM Academic Achievement with Chinese Parents' Participative Styles in School Education</p>	<p>Na, Wang, Yang & Du, China (2018)</p>	<p>Does not describe</p>	<p>Parental Participation • Parents' Participative Styles • STEM</p>	<p>1. Do social economic status of parents and household structure impact academic achievement of Chinese students' STEM subjects? How does each component variable influence academics?</p> <p>2. What influences do parents' participation in cognition, emotion, and behavior have on academic achievement of Chinese students in STEM subjects?</p> <p>3. How do different variables at each dimension of Chinese parents' participation influence their children's academic achievement in STEM?</p>	<p>Parental survey sample data from the China Curriculum and Instruction Research Database (ICIC).</p>	<p>- The emotional participation of the parents has a greater influence. - Parents' satisfaction with their children's school performance can be seen as an aspect of parents' expectations.</p>	<p>An, G., Wang, J., Yang, Y., Du, X. (2018). A Study on the Effects to Students' STEM Academic Achievement with Chinese Parents' Participative Styles in School Education. <i>Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice</i>, 19(1),41-54. DOI 10.12738/estp.2019.1.0180 https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1215165</p>
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Exploring Parent and Teacher Perceptions of Family Engagement	Arce, EUA (2019)	41 students, 3 parents/families and 5 teachers	Does not describe	<p>What are the prevailing attitudes and beliefs about family involvement and engagement among families and teachers at Phoenix Charter School?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What steps can be taken to improve the engagement of families at Phoenix Charter School? <p>Does not describe objective.</p>	Action research, Instrument: Observation. Interview, questionnaire and focus group.	<p>1) There is no collective definition of family involvement, but almost all agreed that families must be proactive in reaching out to educators; 2) Linguistic differences are not being supported, making it difficult for parents and teachers to build relationships; 3) Implicit biases, assumptions and presumptions on behalf of all stakeholders are influencing the decisions and actions of parents and staff.</p>	<p>Arce, S. (2019). Exploring Parent and Teacher Perceptions of Family Engagement. <i>International Journal of Teacher Leadership Exploring</i> 83(10), (2), ISSN: 1934-9726 https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1244923.pdf</p>
Parental Participation in Children's Education: Experiences of Parents and Teachers in Ghana	APPIAH-KUB & One, Ghana (2019)	8 parents and 8 teachers	Parents' motivation, parental participation, school, supervision, teachers	<p>Understand which factors motivate and impede parents' active involvement in their children's education.</p>	Qualitative methodology. Instrument: semi-structured interview.	<p>The results revealed that the parents' belief that their participation in their children's education is part of the training they should give them motivated them to participate.</p> <p>- Barriers to parents' participation in their children's education include the high cost of living that has parents worried. O to the illiteracy of some parents which makes them feel that they cannot offer much beyond paying their children's school fees.</p>	<p>Appiah-Kubi, J., & Amoako, E. O. (2020). Parental participation in children's education: Experiences of parents and teachers in Ghana. <i>Kuramsal Eğitimbilim Dergisi [Journal of Theoretical Educational Science]</i>, 13(3), 456-473. https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1288696</p>
Relationship	Assefa e Sintayeh	52 parents	Parental, Involvement,	To examine the relationship	Correlational research.	- Conclude that there is positive relationship between parental	Assefa, A, & Sintayehu, B. (2019).

between Parental Involvement and Students' Academic Achievement in Model Primary and Secondary School of Haramaya University, East Hararghe Zone, Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia	u, Ethiopia (2019)	and 60 students	Relationship, Academic, Students' Achievement	between parental involvement and students' academic achievement in Model Primary and Secondary School of Haramaya University, Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia	Questionnaires, semi-structured interview and document analysis	involvement and students' academic achievement - The level of parental involvement on supporting their children on their education was moderate	Relationship between Parental Involvement and Students' Academic Achievement in Model Primary and Secondary School of Haramaya University, East Hararghe Zone, Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia. <i>International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies</i> , 7(2),46. https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1219590
How Is Parental Educational Involvement Related to School Satisfaction for Parents of Young Autistic	Schuck, Simpson & Golloher, EUA (2022).	45 parents	Autism spectrum disorder, parental involvement, school satisfaction, skill generalization, autistic children, families	To learn more about satisfaction with and involvement in education using quantitative and qualitative survey data.	Qualitative methodology Instrument: questionnaire	- Parents want to be more involved in school activities. - Significant lack of strategy to involve parents. - It is necessary for educators to encourage parental involvement that will have a positive impact	Schuck, R.K., Simpson, L. A. & Golloher, A.N. (2022). How Is Parental Educational Involvement Related to School Satisfaction for Parents of Young Autistic Children? <i>School Community Journal</i> , 32(1). https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1347523.pdf

Children ?							
The Transition to Kindergarten for Children with and without Special Needs: Identification of Family Experiences and Involvement	Hacıbrahimoglu Turquia (2022)	232 parents	Transition to Kindergarten, Transition, Parent Involvement, Family Experiences, Family Concerns, Preschool	To analyze the experiences and participation of families of children with and without special needs transitioning to kindergarten	-The survey research in which family experiences and involvement in the transition to kindergarten are determined. -The Family Experiences and Involvement in Transition (FEIT; McIntyre et al., 2007)	- Both family groups find information and family involvement useful in the transition process. It has been determined that families with CSN, especially the person responsible for the child's care, need more information about what to do in the transition -Families specifically preferred the family involvement types of meetings and visits; - Show that all families, whether or not they have a child with a disability, want transition-related practices	Hacıbrahimoglu,B,Y.(2022). The Transition to Kindergarten for Children with and without Special Needs: Identification of Family Experiences and Involvement. <i>International Journal of Progressive Education</i> ,18(2). DOI:10.29329/ijpe.2022.431.7 https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1343112.pdf

Table 2 View of articles selected for the study.